

Teaching the rules of writing methodical lesson development for primary education teachers

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Аннотация: В данной научной статье полностью разъясняется разработка урока, правила написания развития урока и требования к нему.

Ключевые слова: разработка урока, форма урока, вид урока, метод урока, девиз урока.

Abstract: In this scientific article, the lesson development, the rules of writing the lesson development and the requirements for it are fully explained.

Key words: lesson development, lesson form, lesson type, lesson method, lesson motto.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy maqolada dars ishlanma, dars ishlanma yozish qoidalari va unga qo'yilgan talablar haqida to'liq yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: dars ishlanma, dars shakli, dars turi, dars metodi, dars shiori.

Lesson development (plan-summary) is a document that is mandatory for the teacher. Lesson development is a factor that determines teacher creativity. A lesson plan is a pedagogical, didactic and methodological planning document. It is not created just to show management. The main purpose of its creation is to plan the activities of the teacher in one hour of the lesson, to enrich the content of the lesson, and to increase the effectiveness of education. Lesson development is a product of the teacher's creative work and is a mirror of his knowledge and skills. Therefore, it is necessary not to rush to draw it up. A well-designed lesson plan can

serve a teacher for many years. This should not lead to the conclusion that lesson development is a frozen dogma.

It is necessary to improve and perfect the lesson development from year to year, to use new teaching methods, and to update it with the introduction of new materials. With the introduction of state educational standards and curricula based on the competence approach, the use of new pedagogical technologies, computers, new information technologies and technical tools in the educational process, the requirements for lesson development are also changing. There are no ready-made templates for lesson plans, because the lesson process cannot be modeled. It can be structured differently under different circumstances.

Nevertheless, teachers are advised to structure the lesson plan based on the following structure: Structure of the lesson plan: 1. Lesson topic. 2. Lesson objectives. 3. Information sources, educational methodical literature and electronic resources used in the lesson. 4. Necessary technical tools and equipment used in the lesson. 5. Lesson form. 6. Type of lesson. 7. Teaching methods. 8. Lesson stages and time distribution. 9. A brief description of the course.

The components of the lesson plan (synopsis) are as follows: Date, class (for parallel classes, it is not necessary to write a separate lesson plan (synopsis) on one topic, it is enough to write one lesson plan on one topic. 5-"A", " B" is indicated as classes), the name of the subject is written. The topic of the lesson (the calendar-topic is selected based on the plan). The goal of the lesson (the goal set for the lesson should be achievable (achievable) within 45 minutes, concrete, vital (real) and evaluated (measurable) at the end of the lesson. The goal of the lesson is determined based on the requirements of the state educational standard. It should be written based on what kind of knowledge, skills and abilities the students will acquire in this lesson, and not with the fact that it should give the students the

following knowledge, skills and abilities. The goal should be expressed in clear, simple and understandable sentences, not lofty and airy. The most important thing is that the goal of the lesson can be really achieved and the result can be checked. The main concepts and terms that should be covered in the lesson are based on the educational content in accordance with the curriculum. is determined.

The purpose of the lesson is 3 different: a) educational purpose - determines the knowledge, skills and abilities formed in the course of the lesson; b) educational goal - determines which personal qualities, moral qualities and spiritual worldview should be created in students during the course of the lesson; c) developmental goal - determines the conditions for the development of students' abilities and special skills as a result of the lesson. Type of lesson: new understanding, knowledge builder; developing students' knowledge, skills and abilities; generalizing; There can be such types of lessons as analysis of the knowledge, skills and qualifications acquired by students, as well as monitoring. Methods used in the lesson. In this case, it is necessary to wisely choose the one that serves the students' effective mastering of the subject from traditional, modern, interactive methods. Equipment used in the lesson. Technical tools, slides, visual and didactic materials. Necessary equipment and sources of information for the lesson include textbooks and other educational literature, visual aids, experimental equipment, models, posters, handouts, evidence, paper, writing and drawing tools, computer, audio and will consist of a list of video equipment and other technical means of teaching. This list should be based on the school's capabilities. Also, in this section, the work to be done before the lesson, the preparation of the classroom for the lesson, the arrangement of tables and chairs or desks according to the lesson, and the list of materials to be prepared, the templates of these materials should be described or attached. Lesson stages and time distribution (or

technological map of the lesson) is a table with several columns, usually the first column shows the main stages of the lesson and the time required for each stage, the second column shows the teacher's activity, and the third shows the student's activity. Lesson details and methodological recommendations form the core of lesson development. It may vary depending on the type of lesson and the chosen method.

The lesson can be divided into the following stages: I. Organizational part. II. Repeat the previous topic. III. Explaining a new topic. IV. Consolidation of a new subject. V. Concluding the lesson and evaluating the students. VI. Homework assignment. It is appropriate for the teacher to take into account each part of the lesson when preparing the lesson plan. Every teacher must have a lesson plan (summary). However, the content, size and number of pages of the lesson should be based on the teacher's unique approach to teaching. It is impossible to set the same limits and restrictions for all teachers.

Lesson development (summary) can be written in handwritten form or on a computer. The sequence of describing the details of the lesson usually consists of the following: 1) organizational part; 2) readiness to start a new topic (repeating past lesson topics related to a new topic; determining and assessing students' knowledge levels related to this topic before moving on to a new topic; explaining the purpose of the new topic); 3) coverage of a new topic (presentation of lesson materials in small parts, sequentially in certain coherence and logical connection in a demonstrative way and using different teaching methods); 4) strengthening of a new topic (applying the acquired theoretical knowledge to concrete examples and completing various tasks, forming practical skills of students on the topic); Completion of the lesson (summary) and homework assignment. Each lesson ends with a conclusion and assignments for students to complete at home. At the end of

the lesson, it is better to give homework to the students individually. It is necessary to give tasks depending on the knowledge potential of each student. Otherwise, if the student cannot independently find answers to questions when doing homework, cannot complete tasks, then he will get bored with science, and he will lose confidence in his abilities. Every teacher should prevent them. At the end of the lesson and giving homework: a) what to pay attention to from the textbook, repeat the topic; b) it is appropriate to give advice on how to complete which tasks. It is recommended to spend 4-5 minutes on this part of the lesson. This should include the standard of homework and how much time the student will spend on it.

In conclusion, we can say that through the development of the lesson, it is necessary to get students to work with the textbook, to read and observe independently, to think logically, and to acquire the concepts of science at a high level.

References:

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